

Crop management

Effect of hill density, seedling number/hill, and potassium on late transplanted *sali* (rainfed lowland winter) rice yield in Assam, India

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Late planting of *sali* (rainfed lowland winter) rice is common in many parts of the Barak Valley zone (Cacher, Karimganj, and Hailakandi districts) of Assam, India, because of flooding during July and August, the normal planting time. Yields are usually low under late planting because of poor tillering and reduced panicle size, resulting from progressive drought and low soil K status. Managing the optimum plant population and K status seems to be

imperative for stabilizing yield under these conditions.

We studied the effect of hill density (HD), seedlings/hill (SH), and K levels on late-planted *sali* rice yield during 1992-93. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (factorial) with three replications. Eighteen treatment combinations of HD (33, 50, and 66 hills/m² maintained at spacings of 20 × 15 cm, 20 × 10 cm, and 15 × 10 cm, respectively), SH (1, 3, and 5), and K levels (20 kg/ha and 40 kg/ha) were tested. Bunds were constructed to separate the 24-m² plots.

The soil was clay loam with pH 5.1, 0.87% organic C, 22 kg available P/ha, and 94 kg available K/ha. Fifty-day-old seedlings of KMJ1-52-3, a photoperiod-sensitive, semidwarf cultivar, were planted on 25 Sep. Recommended doses of N (40 kg/ha), P (20 kg/ha), and K (per treatment) were applied basally. Rice yield was recorded at 14% moisture.

The crop duration was 145-146 d. The treatments involving 33 hills/m², 5 SH and 40 kg K/ha, and 50 hills/m², 5 SH, and 20 kg K/ha recorded the best yields (Table 1). The increased productive tillers/plant at 33-50 hills/m² at 5 SH probably resulted in the better yield performance, although in 1993, 50 hills/m², 3 SH, and 40 kg K/ha produced equally good yields.

The main effects of HD and SH were significant in both years, but for K, in 1993 only (Table 2). Grain yield increased significantly when HD was 33 hills/m² in 1992 and 50 hills/m² in 1993. In both years, yield increased progressively with increase in SH from 1 to 5. The interaction between HD and SH was significant because the treatments involving 5 SH, irrespective of HD, outyielded the rest except for 3 SH and 50 hills/m² in 1993.

Forty kg K/ha recorded a significant yield increase over 20 kg K/ha in 1993. But HD × K interaction was significant in both years, and the treatment involving 33 hills/m² and 40 kg K/ha outyielded the others in 1992. In 1993, 50 hills/m², either at 20 or 40 kg K/ha, yielded at par with 33 hills/m² and 40 kg/ha K. The interaction, HD × SH × K, however, was significant in both years.

Though rainfall was greater in 1992 (903.4 mm) than in 1993 (771.3 mm), less rain during Nov-Dec 1992 (10.8 mm) compared with 1993 (30.4 mm) made a

Table 1. Effect of hill density, seedlings per hill, and K levels on productive tillers/plant^a and grain yield (t/ha)^b of late planted *sali* rice. Assam, India. 1992-93.

Hills/m ² (no.)	1 seedling/hill		2 seedlings/hill		3 seedlings/hill	
	20 kg K/ha	40 kg K/ha	20 kg K/ha	40 kg K/ha	20 kg K/ha	40 kg K/ha
	1992					
33	2.4 e (5)	2.5 e (6)	2.7 d (6)	2.8 cd (7)	2.9 bc (7)	3.1 a (8)
50	2.2 f (6)	2.2 f (6)	2.7 d (7)	2.8 cd (7)	3.0 ab (8)	2.9 bc (7)
66	2.5 e (6)	2.4 e (6)	2.7 d (5)	2.7 d (6)	2.9 bc (6)	2.9 bc (6)
CV (%)	3.09					
	1993					
33	3.3 ef (7)	3.1 fg (7)	3.4 de (7)	3.5 de (8)	3.6 cd (8)	4.1 a (10)
50	3.0 g (8)	3.4 de (8)	3.8 bc (8)	4.0 ab (9)	4.1 a (11)	3.8 bc (8)
66	3.1 fg (7)	3.1 fg (7)	3.0 g (7)	3.3 ef (8)	3.5 de (7)	3.8 bc (8)
CV(%)	3.74					

^aNumbers in parentheses are not significantly different. ^bWithin a year, means either in a column or row followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

Table 2. Grain yield (t/ha) of late-planted rice (KMJ1-52-3) as affected by the interactions of hill density (HD) × seedlings/hill (SH) and HD × K^a. Assam, India. 1992-93.

HD (no./m ²)	Seedlings per hill				K (kg/ha)		
	1	3	5	Mean	20	40	Mean
	1992						
33	2.5 d	2.8 b	3.0 a	2.8	2.7 b	2.8 a	2.8
50	2.2 e	2.8 b	3.0 a	2.7	2.7 b	2.6 c	2.7
66	2.5 d	2.7 c	2.9 a	2.7	2.7 b	2.7 b	2.7
Mean	2.4	2.7	3.0		2.7	2.7	
	1993						
33	3.2 c	3.5 b	3.9 a	3.5	3.4 b	3.6 a	3.5
50	3.2 c	3.9 a	3.9 a	3.7	3.7 a	3.7 a	3.7
66	3.1 c	3.2 c	3.7 a	3.3	3.2 c	3.4 b	3.3
Mean	3.2	3.5	3.8		3.4	3.6	
LSD _(0.05)	1992		1993				
HD × SH means	0.1		0.2				
HD × K means	0.08		0.13				

^aWithin a year and an interaction, means either in a row or a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

difference in the soil moisture status between the years. This might have been the reason for the differential response to K. Plants were adversely affected during the

reproductive and grain-filling stages due to moisture stress, resulting in yield loss, particularly in 1992.

Higher yields of late-planted sali rice

may be achieved by planting 5 SH at 33-50 hills/m². Further investigation is needed regarding K application. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Monitoring variation in brown planthopper biotype in Guangdong, China

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It is important to monitor the variation in brown planthopper (BPH) biotype when breeding resistant varieties. We have been doing this work since 1979 in Guangdong, China, including yearly testing of BPH biotype variation in Guangzhou and conducting a biotype test with BPH populations in Guangdong Province.

We used the seedling bulk test for all of the BPH biotype-monitoring studies. The population for the yearly test of BPH biotype variation was collected from late rice in the field in Guangzhou. The insects were reared on a BPH-susceptible variety in the greenhouse and tested the following year. The BPH population for the biotype test in Guangdong was collected from Guangzhou, Xinhui (central Guangdong), Lechang (northern Guangdong), Xinxing (western Guangdong), and Gaozhou (southwestern Guangdong) in June and July of every year and tested the same year.

Seven BPH-resistant varieties (Table 1) and susceptible check TN1 were evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

In the yearly test of BPH biotype variation in Guangzhou, IR26 had the highest damage score of the varieties including Mudgo, which has the same resistance gene. IR26 was found to be susceptible to BPH in 1992 and 1993 with a score of 7. The score of Mudgo also increased over time. IR36, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, and PTB33 had low

Table 1. Results of biotype test of BPH population of Guangzhou, China.

Year	Damage scale of varieties ^a							
	TN1	IR26 Mudgo		IR36 ASD7 Rathu Heenati		Babawee	PTB33	
	None	<i>Bph</i> 1	<i>bph</i> 2	<i>Bph</i> 3	<i>bph</i> 4	<i>bph</i> 2+ <i>Bph</i> 3		
1979	9.0	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.0	-	-	1.0
1980	9.0	2.8	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1981	9.0	6.7	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1982	9.0	6.6	2.9	5.1	1.1	3.0	3.0	1.0
1983	9.0	4.5	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1984	9.0	3.3	1.0	3.3	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1985	9.0	3.2	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	-	1.0
1986	9.0	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0
1987	9.0	2.9	3.3	1.2	1.1	-	-	1.0
1988	9.0	5.1	1.0	1.4	1.0	-	-	1.0
1989	9.0	6.8	1.0	3.4	3.1	-	-	3.0
1990	9.0	4.9	2.5	2.5	3.2	1.0	-	3.0
1991	9.0	5.2	5.1	3.1	1.0	-	3.0	3.0
1992	9.0	7.0	8.8	3.0	5.2	1.0	5.0	1.0
1993	9.0	7.1	4.9	3.2	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.0

^aAv of 3 replications.

Table 2. Results of biotype test of BPH population of Guangdong, China.^a

Variety	Year	Location						
		Guangzhou	Xinhui	Lechang	Gaozhou	Xinxing	Shantou	Huiyang
TN1	1992	7.7 (1.6) a	7.6 (1.2) ab	9.0 (0.0) a	8.9 (0.2) a	8.3 (0.7) a	8.3 (0.7) ab	8.4 (0.5) a
	1993	7.8 (0.9) a	9.0 (0.0) a					
	1994	8.8 (0.3) a	9.0 (0.0) a	9.0 (0.0) a	8.6 (0.7) ab	8.8 (0.2) a	-	-
IR26	1992	6.8 (1.3) b	6.4 (2.2) bc	8.7 (0.3) a	7.4 (1.3) c	7.9 (1.4) ab	7.6 (1.0) bc	4.7 (1.5) c
	1993	6.8 (0.8) b	9.0 (0.0) a	8.9 (0.2) a	9.0 (0.0) a	7.2 (1.7) bc	8.6 (0.6) a	8.7 (0.3) a
	1994	7.4 (1.2) ab	8.3 (0.7) a	8.9 (0.2) a	8.7 (0.5) a	8.2 (0.3) a	-	-
Mudgo	1992	4.9 (1.9) cd	4.0 (0.4) d	5.0 (2.3) c	5.3 (1.2) d	5.4 (1.7) d	6.7 (1.2) c	6.7 (1.6) b
	1993	5.9 (0.2) bc	6.6 (0.2) b	8.2 (0.9) ab	8.7 (0.0) a	5.4 (0.5) d	6.5 (0.8) c	8.7 (0.6) a
	1994	4.9 (1.7) c	8.8 (0.3) a	7.5 (1.1) b	7.8 (1.4) bc	5.9 (1.0) cd	-	-
IR36	1992	3.1 (0.2) e	1.2 (0.2) e	1.5 (0.5) de	1.0 (0.0) e	1.7 (0.7) g	1.8 (1.3) de	4.9 (0.2) c
	1993	2.7 (1.5) ef	5.6 (1.1) c	1.9 (1.0) d	4.1 (0.6) d	2.3 (1.2) fg	2.3 (1.2) d	3.0 (1.5) d
	1994	3.8 (1.1) de	5.0 (2.1) cd	7.0 (0.8) b	4.7 (1.7) d	4.8 (1.3) de	-	-
ASD7	1992	1.0 (0.0) g	1.1 (0.2) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	2.3 (1.5)de
	1993	1.0 (0.0) g	1.5 (0.9) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	1.1 (0.2) e
	1994	1.1 (0.2) fg	7.8 (0.6) a	3.8 (0.6) c	3.8 (0.7) d	3.7 (0.6) ef	-	-
PTB33	1992	1.3 (0.6) f	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	3.4 (1.4) cd
	1993	1.0 (0.0) g	1.3 (0.6) e	1.5 (0.6) d	1.0 (0.0) e	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) g	1.0 (0.0) e
	1994	1.8 (1.2) f	1.7 (0.8) e	2.3 (1.2) d	1.2 (0.4) e	1.1 (0.2) g	-	-

^aMeans are the av of 3 replications and are compared by LSD test. Means (SD) within each column with the same letter are not significantly different (P>0.05).